

Human Facial Expression Recognition Using Handcrafted Features and Deep Learning

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Abstract: Recognition of facial expressions, a critical aspect of non-verbal social communication, plays an essential role in the field of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). The development and application of both traditional handcrafted features and contemporary deep neural networks (DNNs) have substantially advanced the efficacy of Facial Expression Recognition (FER) systems. Enhancements in deep learning technologies have significantly improved the performance and efficiency of FER methodologies, rendering it an increasingly researched topic, particularly with the advent of streamlined neural network models. In this study, we introduced a framework designed to enhance the precision of Facial Expression Recognition (FER) by integrating sophisticated neural network-derived features with manually crafted features, including structural and appearance-based elements. Specifically, the handcrafted features employed encompass facial landmarks, Histograms of Oriented Gradients (HOG) — applicable with or without sliding window techniques — Local Binary Patterns (LBP), and Scale-Invariant Feature Transforms (SIFT). To effectively amalgamate these diverse features, the proposed model integrates a fully connected (FC) layer of CNN, facilitating the feature fusion of both the handcrafted and deep learning-derived features. Following this integration, the framework employs a CNN-based classification algorithm, which has been validated against benchmark datasets for effectiveness assessment. The evaluation protocol involved utilizing images of size 48×48 pixels to conduct tests and measure the performance of our proposed framework on several challenging datasets, notably FER2013 and the Extended Cohn-Kanade (CK+) datasets. According to the literature review, the presented framework exhibits a significant improvement in test accuracy over prevailing algorithms and methodologies within the domain. In the context of the FER2013 and Extended Cohn-Kanade (CK+) datasets, our system showcased superior performance. Specifically, it achieved accuracy rates of 66.5% and 99.8% across seven distinct emotional states, respectively. These results underscore the effectiveness and reliability of the proposed framework in accurately recognizing facial expressions.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Handcrafted Features, HOG, LBP, SIFT, Feature Fusion, Facial Expression Recognition

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Introduction

Most of the time people prefer expression as a form of nonverbal communication and to depict their feelings. Facial expressions are sometimes used to convey one's feelings and sometimes comprehend the emotional world of others. The renowned American psychologist Mehrabian devised that Non-verbal communication, such as facial expressions and vocal tone, plays a crucial role in conveying emotions. Facial expressions account for the majority of emotional expressions at 55%, while vocal tone and other aspects of our voice contribute 38%. Words only contribute 7% to emotional expression but are still important in communication. Facial expression recognition plays a crucial role in gaining an understanding of human emotions [1]. Multiple domains like image processing, and pattern recognition have been brought up front for face recognition and FER technology in past years, as computers have enhanced power and the Internet has broadened. That is why, face identification and FER technology have exceptional research value and importance [2].

In facial expression, preserving consistency and expression realism during lighting, occlusion, and position of the face change is very crucial. One of two techniques is chosen by the researcher in classic FER systems. Either the complete image data or specific geometric locations used to fetch the features. After all of the image data is analyzed, a huge chunk of data, most of which is undesired, is to process. Machine learning algorithms that analyze only the most important data by ignoring the majority of input are Support vector machines (SVM). Moreover, conventional artificial neural networks (ANN) strive with tiny datasets. To achieve maximum accuracy, ANNs demand an inordinate amount of data and a long span of training time. It's quite difficult to mark the right combination of feature extraction techniques. If enough features cannot be extracted then the rest of the facial geometry will be missed out, as facial features and geometric landmarks. The presented model is different in that it uses a feature extraction method that is applied to a facial image [3].

In this paper, HOG with or without sliding windows, SIFT, facial landmark points, and LBP are popular handcrafted feature extraction methods. HOG is related to the structure or the shape of an image's face. HOG provides edge direction. The gradient and orientation of the edges in an image are extracted to evaluate this. An 8x8 pixel sliding window is effective for implementing HOG in an image. SIFT is used to detect key features in a target image that are invariant to scale, rotation, and illumination changes. LBP controls the most ordinary issues of illumination. 68 landmarks on the face can be used to recognize facial landmarks. Facial landmarks recognize the areas around the jaws, eyebrows, chin, mouth, nose, and eyes correctly.

The convolutional layer is CNN's predominant method of discovering key features. CNN uses the hierarchical expression, and the previous convolutional layer's output feature map is used as the input of the next convolutional layer. The more layers of the network, the more facial expression features to be extracted. By huge number of network layers and parameters also made the overfitting easier. Using a one-way CNN has been seen to be unproductive in evaluating facial expression features. This paper uses CNN with dense FC layers to learn facial expression identification. the FC layer is used while combining CNN features and handcrafted features. And then, in the classification (Softmax) layer features are classified. Two majorly used facial expression datasets, FER2013 and CK+ for experiments. The average recognition accuracy of our presented method is higher.

Literature Review

During the 2013 FER Challenge many of the initial experiments, which utilized deep learning to FER, were brought up upfront. The best-handcrafted model held the fourth spot while on the other hand, a deep CNN came up as the best scorer in the 2013 FER Challenge. Most of the present FER research, excluding only a few [4], is based on deep learning. Others [5], and [6] integrated deep features with handcrafted features like SIFT or HOG while a variety of these recent articles [7], and [8] proposed the training of a group of CNNs for better achievement.

Aligned face expression recognition system research that has been done so far has been discussed. Features of these algorithms, which are handcrafted and deep-learned, may be roughly separated into two categories. Geometric-based

and appearance-based features are two types of feature extraction algorithms for facial images based on the Handcrafted feature extraction method. To find out facial geometry-related features facial landmarks (and other shapes) are being utilized to identify and detect facial features. There are low-level features to collect information on the texture and look of the face (i.e., appearance-based features). We utilize the Geometric Elements Extractor to take out geometric elements of the facial structure and facial muscle motion for the specific purpose of geometric feature extraction. Face-centered geometric embedding for whole automatic learning of the extracted facial features is used for the extraction of appearance features. CNN, which uses diverse layers of the network to attain deep learning functionality, is used for deep learning-based feature extraction [9].

To take out the face's landmark, temporal, or dynamic alterations, the geometric features algorithm is employed. For expression representation, the geometric connection between landmark points identified from facial regions is used. Several geometric features, while using both psychology and physiology, are produced by the research team. An end-to-end deep learning method is presented by Zhang et al. that makes use of the geometry of the face image to synthesize concurrent facial images and recognize facial expressions that remain firm when the face is in a certain posture (e.g., neutral, happy, etc.) [10]. If the landmark points are identified erroneously the identification precision will be lessened. For elaborating facial expressions, which utilize local appearance information, LBP is the most often used appearance-based method. It is used to explore the contrast within image sub-regions. In the conventional arrangement, a pixel is in contrast with its eight neighbors. An 8-bit binary pattern is resulted. The LBP descriptor histogram may be kept. The face feature with a binary pattern layout is represented by each histogram bin. To describe a 256-dimensional descriptor, here is how it is done. The look of most individuals is not easy to elaborate on. The appearances of people may change with time which is the central drawback of appearance-based approaches. The histogram of gradients (HOG) was established to assist with object recognition and pedestrian identification. To assist with face recognition and extract HOG features from photos of faces, while utilizing a dense grid, Lazebnik et al. [11] used HOG descriptors. Bosch et al. defined a new PHOG descriptor, for the form of a facial area, which they extracted from the HOG descriptor. There has been seen a wide use of deep learning in multiple computer vision applications, including FER, with unexpected consequences. The facial expression features are automatically learned by CNN. Dong et al. utilized robust connectivity across pooling to confirm feature sharing in a shallow CNN structure so that facial expression identification with coherent speed and a restricted training set could be carried out. The major features of deep learning are utilized by this study to raise the generalization potential of facial expression detection for the deep convolutional neural network [12]. A new neural network that utilizes domain information loss and dynamic goals learning [13] to help avoid gradient drift is developed by Wen et al.

Wang created the Self-Cure Network (SCN), an easy-to-use yet successful technique for averting precariousness and inhibiting deep networks from overfitting uncertain facial images. There is a possibility of accomplishing a greater identification rate, using deep learning-based approaches, but it would require more computing resources and data. That is the reason why the conventional framework has been utilized in this study. A refined identification performance has been exhibited by those Studies that looked at training an ensemble of CNNs.

On the other hand, such studies that evolve around deep features with handcrafted features, such as SIFT and HOG [5] manifested parallel outcomes. Having the dynamic nature of facial expressions compelled [6] to use Video data instead of static images. A 2-channel CNN with the use of a convolutional autoencoder (FER) was created by Hamester et al. (i.e., a normal CNN and a channel that employs pre-trained parameters). Additionally, previous research which is documented in [5], [6] illustrates that FER methods presented in this work are related to prior studies. In both approaches, deep features and handcrafted features are merged.

Further studies, in conjunction with FER, have also utilized deep and handcrafted features [14] or local learning. Local learning may also be used to enhance a handcrafted model's performance as illustrated by Ionescu et al. A unitary CNN model is employed, most of the time, by the Works that integrate deep and handcrafted features mostly with a diversity

of handcrafted features, such as SIFT and dense SIFT in Connie et al. [5], and SIFT, HOG, and Local Gabor Binary Patterns in Kaya et al. [6]. (LGBP). We use multiple handcrafted features and merge them with one sort of CNN architecture. The incorporation of both deep and handcrafted features is another significant variation between works [5], [6]. Even so, it has been illustrated by our static image tests that several state-of-the-art methods have been outperformed because of the combination of the suggested model. Extracting deep convolutional features and combining them with a large number of handcrafted descriptors, such as appearance and shape features, is what we suggest.

Dataset Acquisition & Pre-Processing

To demonstrate the results of the model we suggested, we conducted several face recognition experiments utilizing two publicly accessible datasets FER2013 and the CK+ dataset.

A. Dataset Acquisition and Preparation

CK+ Dataset: The CK+ dataset comprises 593 video sequences from 123 individuals in the CK+ Extended Database, featuring six distinct facial expressions. For the experiment, Three key frames from each sequence were extracted, totaling 981 images that prominently represent the expression tensor. Figure 1 showcases a subset of sample images from the CK+ database.

FER2013 Dataset: The FER2013 database, includes seven distinct facial expressions, namely Disgust, Fear, Sad, Surprise, Happy, Angry, and Neutral. The training set comprises 28,709 training data points, while the validation set involves 3,589 public test data points, and the private test data consists of an additional 3,589 distinct samples (test set). Each image is a 48×48-pixel grayscale representation. Due to its non-laboratory acquisition, this dataset presents real-life facial expressions affected by various interfering factors such as occlusion, side face views, and varying angles, making identification challenging. A subset of the FER2013 database sample is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Sample images from CK+ database

Fig. 2. Sample images from FER2013 database.

B. Image Preprocessing

Preprocessing is required for any identification field. For FER, image noise and reinforced imperative information can drop with specialized preprocessing, therefore strengthening- overall system performance. Face recognition, cropping, grayscale transformation, and rescale are among the image preprocessing techniques that are utilized. These techniques are used to enhance the model’s performance. It can minimize the imbalance among training samples while also shrinking computational storage and accelerating the training process when used in conjunction with other techniques. HOG with an SVM, Haar cascade, and CNN models have all been exhibited as face recognition algorithms. Because of its quick processing speed, in this study, we use the DLIB library to locate faces, as shown in Figure 1. DLIB incorporates a pre-trained model as a facial landmark detector. The model single out multiple facial areas constituted by 68 different points upon the face. To accomplish a more distinctive and precise facial dataset, the Image resizes into 48×48 to pursue standardized all faces, without consideration of race, gender, or data gathering conditions. This perspective guarantees that the amplitudes of geometric feature components are allocated firmly in feature space. Because CNN works by extracting features from grayscale images in this paper. We transform the image into a grayscale for that motive. A grayscale image works as the input. The output layer is a binary or multi-class labeling system.

Research Methodology

An inclusive framework for FER is presented in this paper. It is comprised of the processes of facial image preprocessing feature extraction, feature fusion, and classification.

A. Handcrafted Features

Face landmark: We employ the DLIB package to identify points of faces for Geometric feature extraction. It provides us with the 68 (x,y) coordinates that correlate with the sole facial features in the image for each of the face recognitions. Consequently, an array of the shapes (68, 2) is discovered, which helps in face identification, face adjustment, and cropping image border selection. Fundamentally, emotions are naturally transmitted by the brows, eyes, nose, and some facial regions therefore the forehead and ears are further parts of the face that can be ignored.

Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT): This uses the main direction of the neighborhood region around a feature point to establish its orientation. The output of this step is a 128-dimensional feature descriptor, which is used as the basis for matching features between images. The SIFT feature extraction method relies on identifying significant points of interest within an object, making it resistant to changes in the size and orientation of the image.

Local Binary Pattern (LBP): There is chosen a circular Local Binary Pattern with a radius of 24 points (LBP) for every image collection. Feature extraction is accomplished by utilizing a non-rotational invariant stable approach. A 26-dimensional histogram was used as a feature extractor in conjunction with an image processing technique. Consequently, the notion of LBP homogeneity was born. In LBP, if there are a maximum of two 0-1 or 1-0 transitions, it is labeled smooth. When rotationally invariant features are desired, there exist $p + 1$ uniform patterns for an LBP with p number of points. The dimension of the histogram becomes $p \times (p-1) + 3$ when LBP features, do not hold rotation information for the non-rotational invariant uniform approach. Rotation variation is created by the camera or the recorded images rotating. As it exhibits how local micro-patterns like edges, spots, and flat regions are allocated across the entire image, this LBP histogram can be used as a feature extractor.

Histogram Of Oriented Gradients (HOG): we utilize the HOG to encode these facial features. In our experiments, we utilized a cell size of 8×8 , several bins of 9, and an orientation value of 8. Sliding windows are also applied to create HOG descriptors. We cut each input image into 24×24 windows with 6 window steps, according to. Blocks of windows are then constructed. Once we have all of the HOG features for all of the frames, we can employ the sliding window method for all of the regions.

Feature Fusion: Feature fusion of various handcrafted features is commonly utilized as one type of feature never constitutes each image attribute. All face features (facial landmarks, LBP, SIFT, and HOG features) are synthesized in this paper. Therefore, a high-dimensional feature vector is originated. Consequently, the dimension of the feature vector of handcrafted features is surged while the identification accuracy is preserved. We acquired the final combined handcrafted feature in this fashion. Eventually, employing dropout and the incorporation of a new FC layer, we became capable of minimizing the number of features from 9922 to 128.

B. Deep Features Extraction

This study aimed to gauge the functioning of trained CNNs such as AlexNet, ZFNet, VGGNet, GoogLeNet, and ResNet concerning classification bug rate and layer count, both of which have an influence on calculation time. We tailored the CNN model, especially for our research. For that specific goal, we crafted another fully connected layer near the feature-generating FC layer. We were capable of minimizing the number of features from 4096 to 128 with dropout by putting in a new completely connected layer, which improved the pace of our approach. The number of neurons was assessed by trial and error. In the end, 128 deep features were extracted.

C. Classification

We merged the deep and handcrafted features by combining the appropriate feature vectors with the help of a new fully connected layer before the learning stage. We took the finishing FC layer of the deep feature and handcrafted feature with a 128 output and merged the two FC layers with a 256 output. This is the combining layer for the softmax layer, which is employed for classification. Consequently, the amalgamated features possess a significant discriminant potential.

We inserted the amalgamated features with a value of 256 into the Softmax layer to compute the FER identification results, as appeared in Figure 3. We evaluate the distinction between the recognition result and the target label, employ the cross-entropy loss function to upgrade the bug in the parameter optimization process, change the weight parameters up until the loss function converges to a bottom value, and then terminate the training.

Experiments and Results

We have organized multiple face recognition experiments on two publicly accessible datasets (FER2013 [15] and CK+ dataset [16]) to illustrate the outcomes of we proposed model. Our research uses TensorFlow resources to prepare CNN architectures for the identification of expression states and prediction of expression states.

We assessed the efficacy of our model, across a variety of metrics such as true positive and negative rates, and the confusion matrix. The simulation results and a comprehensive analysis of the performance of each model are delineated in the ensuing sections. Detailed simulation results and a thorough analysis of each model’s performance are provided in the following sections

Fig. 3. The Working Flow of the Proposed Facial Expression Recognition Approach.

Before presenting the evaluation results for each model, a brief overview of the primary evaluation metrics used in this research is outlined: Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. Precision, also referred to as Positive Predictive Value, gauges the proportion of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positives. The metric Recall, alternatively recognized as Sensitivity or True Positive Rate, assesses the proportion of accurately

$$Precision = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive + False\ Positive}$$

Predicted positive observations concerning the total genuine positives. It is computed as:

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive + False\ Positive}$$

The F1-Score represents the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, offering a balanced assessment between these two metrics. It is formulated as:

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

that we have established the definitions of Precision, Recall, and F1-Score, we proceed to unveil the evaluation results of our model. Experiment 1: In this experiment, the K-anonymity privacy model is employed to address concerns related to identity disclosure. Figure 1 illustrates the values of k for the K-anonymity model. In Figure 1, a comparison is presented for the risk factors associated with the three mentioned attacker models. To assess the effectiveness of the applied privacy model, the granularity of the output data is computed. The k-anonymity parameter, k, was varied with

values ranging from 2 to 25. As depicted in Figure 1, increasing the value of k correlates with a decrease in the risk of re-identifying a person's information. However, this comes at the cost of losing granularity in the data. The K-anonymity model aims to safeguard the identities of individuals in a dataset by ensuring that each individual cannot be re-identified from fewer than k-1 other individuals.

A. FER2013 Experiments

The images were decreased in the face area to 48 × 48 pixels in size. We entail detecting the hyperparameters by doing parameter optimization so that CNN performance can be improved. Counting all expression levels, with the findings proposed as the average of the ten replications, each experiment was run ten times on the whole dataset. The input data was fused with handmade and deep features autonomously and the proposed system took full advantage of the fusion features. Table I is here to contrast our findings to those of other approaches that have been previously published.

Table 1. Recognition accuracy comparison with state-of-the-art methods on the FER2013 database

Related Work	Accuracy
AlexNet [17]	64.2%
HOG+CNN [14]	61.8%
CNN [18]	65.97%
CNN+LBP+HOG [19]	61.86%
Multi-level Fusion [20]	65.4%
CNN+kernal size and number of filters [21]	65%
Our proposed framework	66.5%

In Experiment, all features (CNN + Face landmarks + HOG + sliding window + LBP + SIFT) outperformed CNN/ CNN + Face landmarks/ CNN + Face landmarks + HOG/ CNN + Face landmarks + HOG + sliding window. Table 2 compares our findings to those of other approaches already published.

Table 2. Shows Precision, Recall, F1-Score Of FER2013

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Angry	0.52	0.53	0.52
Disgust	0.83	0.62	0.71
Fear	0.53	0.51	0.52
Happy	0.81	0.83	0.82
Sad	0.51	0.49	0.50
Surprise	0.78	0.79	0.78
Neutral	0.61	0.64	0.62

Fig. 4. The confusion matrix on FER2013 data

Fig. 5. The confusion matrix on the CK+ dataset

Finally, a confusion matrix 4 was utilized to present a more granular analysis of the proposed model’s classification performance. The matrix revealed an accuracy of 0.665.

B. CK+ Experiments

The procedure utilized for the CK+ database experiments was the identical to FER 2013 database experiments. To take out all of the facial expression images video sequences were employed. During the Experiment, the results of all features (CNN + Face landmarks + HOG + sliding window + LBP + SIFT) were finer than the outcome of CNN/ CNN + Face landmarks/ CNN + Face landmarks HOG/ CNN + Face landmarks + HOG + sliding window. Table III expresses a correlation of our findings with those of other approaches. The suggested framework had a better identification rate (99.8%) over one recent method (97.5%) based on the CK+ dataset.

Table 3. Recognition Accuracy Comparison With State-Of-The-Art Methods On The CK+ Database

Related Work	Accuracy
LBP and CNN [22]	96.48%
Attention Net [23]	97.5%
Transfer Learning using VGG 16 [15]	94.84%
LBP and SVM [24]	91.66%
CNN [24]	97.32%
Our proposed framework	99.8%

Table 4. Shows Precision, Recall, F1-Score Of CK+

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Angry	1.00	1.00	1.00
Contempt	1.00	1.00	1.00
Disgust	1.00	1.00	1.00
Fear	1.00	1.00	1.00
Happy	1.00	1.00	1.00
Sad	0.91	1.00	0.95
Surprised	1.00	0.95	0.98

A confusion matrix was constructed for the seven facial expression classifications. Notably, the precision, recall, and F1-Score values denote the accuracy of the model in correctly identifying specific emotional expressions. The values indicate the model's performance in recognizing distinct emotions such as Angry, Contempt, Disgust, Fear, Happy, Sad, and Surprised. Particularly, the results demonstrate that the model achieved perfect precision, recall, and F1-Score for expressions like Anger, Contempt, Disgust, Fear, and Happiness, indicating flawless performance in identifying these emotions. However, it slightly faltered in distinguishing the Sad and Surprised expressions, achieving a slightly lower F1-Score.

Conclusion

In the fields of computer vision and artificial intelligence, FER was a long-standing difficult research challenge. This article attempted to investigate the full potential of feature fusion and offered a useful framework for doing so. To integrate the diversity of features from the training data, famous handcrafted feature extraction methods such as SIFT, LBP, and HOG with or without sliding windows, and face landmarks and deep features were employed. To leverage the potential of feature fusion approaches in classification, advanced machine learning techniques such as Convolutional Neural Networks are utilized. The Deep Feature and Training model we propose is a small-scale model having fewer layers than competing deep learning models. The suggested framework outperformed the originally handcrafted features and the deep feature on the FER2013, and CK+ databases, according to the experimental findings. The maximum accuracy of FER is highest with an accuracy of 66.5%, and an accuracy of 99.8% on CK+. Competitive results were shown that we achieved state-of-the-art results on the CK+ dataset.

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